

REMOVAL OF LEAD AND CADMIUM IONS FROM AQUEOUS MEDIUM BY MOF COMPOSITE (MIL-101-1,2-DICHLOROETHANE)

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Abstract

Metal organic frameworks (MOFs), have got significant attention over other adsorbents in the last decade. This is basically due to porosity in structure which welcomes host molecules. Metal organic frameworks (MOFs), emerged like excellent porous materials which are now used as adsorbents due to large surface area, permanent porosity and bulk structure. MOFs can be synthesized by both organic and inorganic linkers and metal ion, which results to create extensive three dimensional frameworks. MOFs have some advantages over conventional adsorbents as greater adsorption capacity, large surface area, functional porosity, ordered structure and recyclability. Possible fields of application range from gas adsorption and storage, catalysis, molecular sieving and chemical sensors. In this research work adsorption of heavy metals (Lead and Cadmium) ions on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite is studied, for this MIL-101 is synthesized. X-Ray diffraction technique and FT-IR were used to confirm crystalline structure of MIL-101. Adsorption capability was enhanced by making MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. In order to conduct adsorption experiments, solutions of different concentrations of salts of Lead acetate and Cadmium chloride were prepared and these metals ions were adsorbed on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. Adsorption of heavy metals (Lead and Cadmium) ions on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite were studied by X-Ray diffraction technique and ICP. Langmuir and Freundlich models reveal the adsorption of metals, and these models show that MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite has good adsorption capacity. Langmuir and Freundlich model effectively explains adsorption of heavy metals The concentration of Lead ions was 557 mg/g and the concentration of Cadmium ions was 608 mg/g adsorbed on the surface of 1, 2-Dichloroethane-MIL-101 composite.

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable environmental practices, economic growth, and human health all depend on clean water. Millions of people worldwide depend on having access to safe drinking water, which supports many fundamental aspects of civilization. Due to the negative consequences that environmental contamination of heavy metals is having on people all over the world, it is becoming a bigger issue.

Because of inappropriate waste management, pesticides, fertilizers, and fast expanding agriculture and metal industries, inorganic contaminants are ending up in our rivers, soils, and environment. The metal with density over 5 g.cm⁻³ is called heavy metal. For human heavy metals, even in low level, is considered to be a dangerous [1]. More than 1.2 billion people did not have access to clean water for

drinking at the time. Industries, power plants release toxic chemicals to environment to damage environment. This condition is so dangerous for human life, which is causing different diseases. 2 million tons of pollutants releasing into water which is causing different diseases and killing around 14 000 people daily [2-5]. Water pollutants consist of many components either organic or inorganic by human activities. Lot of metals which are highly toxic for life which are non-biodegradable, are dumping in to water and our food chain are big threat for human life [6]. In the aquatic life arsenic (As) is known as one of very toxic substances among the all of the contaminants. If Arsenic (As) is exposed for long time in water then it will cause cancer, and even death. A very dangerous fact is that, arsenic compounds can be accumulate in human body by the food chain [7]. According to (WHO) the level of arsenic in drinking water is 10 ppb. Emerging Industries and power plants release arsenic to environment to damage environment [8]. Arsenic (As) compounds are widely toxic then other contaminants, because these can easily accumulated by the food chain and causing serious disease like lungs and skin cancers [9-11]. Arsenic in lower oxidation state is more dangerous than in higher oxidation state and its removal from lower oxidation state is more difficult than in higher oxidation state. So As (III) is oxidized to As(V) then it is removed [12]. Arsenic is important because it is used in pigments, veterinary, medicine, ceramics, light filters, fireworks, herbicides, insecticides, fungicides and feed for animals [13]. Lead is one of the highly emerging contaminant of the world 540,000 deaths are recorded in 2016. The International Agency for Research on Cancer declared lead is carcinogenic compound. Lead is causing disability on large scale [14]. Almost every environmental compartment including air, water, and sediments consist of mercury [15]. According to WHO, mercury level in ground water and surface water is less than 0.5 µg/L. Mercury release from broken thermometer is very toxic for inhalation and it can approach in lungs and cause dangerous health hazards [16-17]. Cadmium is used in lot of daily life products like in the production of batteries, plastic stabilizers, coatings, and ironless alloys. That's why after usage it is dumped in to water bodies and causing immense

threat for human life. Cadmium is declared as carcinogenic compound which are threatening human and aquatic life. In Europe Cadmium levels were also found in the surface soils near the industry is increasing vigorously. Cadmium is highly threatening plants and animals, microorganisms due to its high mobility [18]. The major sources of cadmium toxicity are food. It is spreading by cigarette smoking significantly. Except this, it is used in cadmium-nickel battery industry, electroplating, paint pigments and electroplating. If Cadmium compounds dumped into water and stay there for long time, these can affect nutrients, photosynthesis, and respiration development and plant growth due to its adverse effects [19-20].

Metal organic frameworks (MOFs), have got significant attention over other adsorbents in the last decade. This is basically due to porosity in structure which welcomes host molecules. These characteristics make excellent host adsorbent for incoming guest materials. MOFs are defined as bonding between metal ions and ligands [21]. MOFs can be synthesized by both organic and inorganic linkers and metal ion, which results to create extensive three dimensional frameworks.

MOFs yield open frameworks that results extremely large advantages due to of permanent pores area, stable framework and pore volume. Large storage area and extraordinary adsorption sites within MOFs is due to porosity [22-23]. MOFs have shown variety of applications in lot of fields such as adsorption, catalysis, hydrogen storage, drug delivery, gas separation, gas storage, catalysis, sensing material, separation and water purification [24-36]. Advance class of porous materials such as metal-organic materials (MOMs) having MOFs and MOPs (metal-organic polyhedral) are synthesized by a strategy which was also proved successful is self-assembly [37]. Heavy metal ions are huge source of water pollution and these are released by fertilizer, pigment industries, paint, electroplating and metal finishing etc, which have lot of harmful effects on environment. Clean water is big problem all over the world for drinking. Heavy metals are polluting water on large scale and these emerging by intensive industrial activities and as a result these have adverse effect on human health. Heavy metals are so toxic and create so many physiological disorders [38].

Heavy metals pollutants are damaging aquatic life and these can reach tissues through the food [39]. Since last decades various industries are developed so quickly and there industries are releasing pollutants such as cationic and anionic ions, which are very toxic for environment [40-41]. Elimination of heavy metals from water gets great importance since last 20 years. To get best results, porous materials introduced to improved metal uptake capacity [42].

Metal organic frameworks (MOFs) are modifiable pores and cage like structure. These are excellent adsorbent for variety of host materials [43]. For elimination of these heavy metals from water, several techniques are introduced like, chemical precipitation [44], membrane filtration [45], ion exchange [46], adsorption [47]. Most discussed and explained materials in last decade are Metal organic frameworks (MOFs). Most of the applications of MOFs are due to their property of porosity and functionality from organic linkers and metals. Moreover, another specialty of these materials is the tunability of their pore size from micro to meso scale by varying the nature of organic linkers and connectivity of inorganic group. For more functionality/stability and ease of selectivity and preparation of operation the properties of MOFs can be made better by combining with other suitable materials [48-51].

2. Experimental

Synthesis of MIL-101 by hydrothermal method, synthesis of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite, preparation of solutions of heavy metal

(Lead and Cadmium) ions, adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions on surface of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite were studied by FT-IR, PXRD and ICP technique are presented in this section.

Chromium nitrate nonahydrate (99%, CAS No. 7789-02-8), Benzenedicarboxylic acid (99%, CAS No. 84-74-2), Dimethyl formamide (98% , CAS No. 68-12-2), Toluene (99%, CAS No.108-88-3), 1,2-Dichloroethane (99%, CAS No.107-6-2), Lead acetate dehydrate (99%, CAS No.6080-56-4) and Cadmium chloride monohydrate (99%, CAS No. 35658-65-2), all these chemicals were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

2.1 Synthesis of MIL-101 MIL-101 was synthesized by using organic linker Benzenedicarboxylic acid (BDC) 5mmol (2.75g) and Chromium nitrate nonahydrate $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 5mmol (0.83g). 20ml Dimethyl formamide (DMF) was used in this synthetic procedure. Benzenedicarboxylic acid (BDC) and Chromium nitrate nonahydrate $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added to Dimethyl formamide (DMF). This mixture was placed for stirring for half an hours. Then it was poured in teflon vial and placed in autoclave for 20 hours at 220°C. Green crystals were formed. The particles were suspended in a liquid medium and placed in a centrifuge tube and separated from solvent by centrifugation. The crystals were washed with Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), Dichloromethane (DCM), acetone and water. Then dried up to 100°C for 24 hours.

Figure 1 MOF Synthetic Scheme and Structure

MOF crystals were dried and analyzed by spectroscopic technique, Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy. This MOF was also characterized by X-ray diffraction technique.

2.2 Grafting of 1, 2-Dichloroethane MIL-101 is prepared by hydrothermal technique. Coordination unsaturated sites (CUS) are generated in MIL-101 after dehydration at 100°C for 24 hours. Grafting of 1,2-Dichloroethane increases adsorption. 1.0 gram MIL-101 was used with 45 ml 1,2-Dichloroethane in 25 ml of anhydrous toluene. This mixture was refluxed at 60°C for 48 hours. At the end sample was collected by filtration and washed with excess amount of ethanol, then dried at 100°C for 24 hours.

2.3 Adsorption scheme for heavy metal ions

2.3.1 Adsorption of Lead ions To prepare solution of 5.0 mg/L, 7.5 mg/L, 10.0 mg/L, 12.5 mg/L, 15.0 mg/L and 17.5 mg/L, the stock solution was prepared. To prepare stock solution, 5 mg of Lead acetate was dissolved in 50ml of distilled water in 100 ml volumetric flask. When Lead acetate dissolved, the volume filled up to the mark. 10 mg of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane was added to 100 ml of above mentioned concentrations and kept these solutions for 48 hours for adsorption. After 48 hours MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite was separated by centrifugation. Solutions were analysed by ICP analysis to calculate the amount of Pb (II) adsorbed on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite.

Figure 2 Adsorption scheme of heavy metal ions

2.3.2 Adsorption of Cadmium ions Solutions of 5mg/L, 7.5 mg/L, 10.0 mg/L, 12.5 mg/L, 15.0 mg/L and 17.5 mg/L were prepared. 10 mg of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane was added to 100 ml of above mentioned concentrations and kept these

solutions for 48 hours for adsorption. After 48 hours MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite was separated by centrifugation. Solutions were analysed by ICP analysis to calculate the amount of Cd (II) adsorbed on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite.

2.3.3 FT-IR Analysis In FT-IR spectrum of MIL-101, peaks were obtained at 830cm^{-1} , 1506cm^{-1} , 1651cm^{-1} , 3373cm^{-1} and 660.05cm^{-1} and in FT-IR spectrum of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite, additional peaks were obtained at 747.19 cm^{-1} , 2951.13 cm^{-1} and 3448.19 cm^{-1} . Peak at 840 cm^{-1} was obtained during adsorption of Lead ions and peak at 864 cm^{-1} was obtained during adsorption of Cadmium ions.

2.3.4 PXRD Analysis In PXRD spectrum of MIL-101, peaks were obtained at 6.5\AA , 8.9\AA and 10.8\AA and in PXRD spectrum of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite, peaks at 6.5\AA and 10.8\AA were different from peaks of spectrum of MIL. In case of Lead and Cadmium ions adsorption, high intensity peak at 16\AA and small intensity peaks at 17\AA were obtained.

3.1 FT- IR Spectrum

Figure 3.a IR Spectrum of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite

MIL-101 was characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy. Resulting peaks arise between 600cm^{-1} to 4000cm^{-1} which helps to identify different functional groups. Strong and medium bands in spectrum of MIL-101, confirmed the presence of different functional groups in MIL-101. The C-O bending is observed, peak at 1506cm^{-1} shows C=C stretching, at 1651cm^{-1}

3. Results and discussion

This section includes the study of adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions on the surface of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite, for determination of adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions, qualitative and quantitative analyses were performed. Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy and Powder X-Ray diffraction (PXRD) analysis were used for the qualitative determination of adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions, Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) analysis was done for quantitative determination of adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions.

¹ shows C=O characteristic peak and broad peak at 3373cm^{-1} O-H stretching. Polymeric structure of MIL-101 is formed by linkage of Benzenedicarboxylic acid and chromium which is shown by medium peak at 660.05cm^{-1} confirming C-Cr (Carbon-Chromium) bond vibration. This peak confirms the linkage between oxygen of Benzenedicarboxylic acid and

chromium. There are three new peaks in the spectrum of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite which confirms coordination between MIL-101 and 1,2-Dichloroethane this medium peak arise at 747.19 cm^{-1} in spectrum. There is a peak in spectrum of

MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite after adsorption of Lead ions which arise at 840 cm^{-1} and adsorption of Cadmium ions which arise at 864 cm^{-1} . These peaks reveals coordination between MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite and heavy metal ions.

Figure 3. b. IR-Spectrum of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite for adsorption of Lead ions, c. FTIR-Spectrum of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite for adsorption of Cadmium ions

3.2 PXRD Spectrum of MIL-101

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the MIL-101 is shown in figure 4, a. The X-ray powder diffraction data reveals the crystallinity of the metal organic framework (MOF). Apparently, the diffraction peaks of these materials are identical with the reported peaks of MIL-101. MIL-101 has peaks at 6.5Å, 8.9Å and 10.8Å. These peaks prove the crystalline structure of MIL-101. MOF composite was characterized by PXRD. Diffraction peak of MIL-101-

1,2-Dichloroethane composite and MIL-101 were similar at 8.9Å, due to coordination between 1,2-Dichloroethane and MIL-101, diffraction peaks of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite were found different from MIL-101 at 6.5Å and 10.8Å. These adsorption peaks confirmed the coordination between 1,2-Dichloroethane-MIL-101 composite. In case of Lead and Cadmium ions adsorption, high intensity peak at 16Å and small intensity peaks at 17Å was observed.

Figure 4.a XRD of MIL-101 .b PXR of MIL-101 and 1, 2-dichloroethane MIL-101 composite

Figure 4.c PXR D of Metal adsorption on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite

3.3 Adsorption of Lead and Cadmium ions

Adsorption is affected by initial concentrations of Lead and Cadmium ions and the results are shown in figure 5 a, b. The adsorption capacity was gradually increased and then became constant. Experiments were performed for the adsorption of

Lead ions by MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite from solutions having different concentration. The ICP technique of metal ions was used to find out the amount of metal ions adsorbed on the MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite.

Figure 5.a Adsorption of Lead ions on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite b. Adsorption of Cadmium ions on MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite

3.4 Adsorption Isotherm for Arsenic and Fluoride ions

To determine the adsorption mechanism involved in the process, the adsorption kinetics of Lead and

Cadmium ions by MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane have been studied. Adsorption kinetics show how the amount of Lead and Cadmium at the separate solution interface is controlled by the contact time

and the rate of dissolved adsorption. The adsorption process design depends on this calculable rate. The data in the investigation of the adsorption process and the diffusion rate-controlling phases are assessed using kinetic models. Generally, a number of prominent adsorption kinetic models, such as the Langmuir model (Equation 1) for mono layer adsorption and Freundlich models (Equation 2) for multi layer adsorption, have been used to study the mechanism and kinetics of the metal ions uptake process.

$$\frac{1}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{q_{max}C_e} + \frac{1}{q_{max}K_L} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$\text{Log } Q_e = \frac{1}{n} \text{Log } C_e + \text{Log } K_F \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

In these equations K_L ($L.mg^{-1}$) is the Langmuir constant, K_F ($mg.g^{-1}$) is Freundlich constant which shows the affinity between an adsorbate and adsorbent, q_{max} ($mg.g^{-1}$) represents the maximum adsorption capacity, C_e ($mg.L^{-1}$) represents initial concentration of adsorbate and Q_e ($mg.L^{-1}$) represent concentration of adsorbate which is absorbed by adsorbent. The best fitted parameters are reported in Table 3, and the experimental findings are displayed in Fig.6 along with the Langmuir and Freundlich fitting lines. In this instance, a multilayer adsorption process is indicated by the Freundlich model's significantly higher correlation coefficients R^2 .

Table.1 Adsorption of Lead and Cadmium ions

Adsorption of Lead ions		
Model	Factors	Values
Langmuir	R^2	0.78727
	m	1.02304
	K_L	3.02 L/mg
Freundlich	R^2	0.99018
	n	0.889
	K_f	48.7 L/mg
Adsorption of Cadmium ions		
Model	Factors	Values
Langmuir	R^2	0.95171
	m	0.94032
	K_L	12.75 L/mg
Freundlich	R^2	0.97908
	n	1.97
	K_f	1.22 L/mg

Figure 6.a Langmuir Adsorption Isotherm for Lead ions b. Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm for Lead ions c. Langmuir Adsorption Isotherm for Cadmium ions d. Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm for Cadmium ions

3.5 Effect of pH value on the adsorption of Lead and Cadmium ions

The pH values influence adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions, pH value is significant factors that can increase the absorption of heavy metal ions. Binding sites on the surface of the adsorbent nature of the adsorbent are affected by pH values. The

pH of the solution is a significant parameter has an influence on surface area of the adsorbent. The pH of the solution describes the extent of ionization of the adsorbate and the degree of dissociation of the functional groups of adsorbent. So the pH is key factor that explain adsorption process from a small laboratory scale to large industrial scale.

Figure 7.a The effect of pH value on adsorption of Lead ions b. The effect of pH value on adsorption of Cadmium ions

Adsorption of heavy metal ions by the effect of pH was investigated in this work, and results represented which are given in figure 7. The adsorption results shows that the adsorption efficiency increased at the pH 6. The pH value of the solution describes the adsorption ability of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite which is used as adsorbent. The pH value of the solution can change the charge of adsorbent surface. The pH value also controls the existence of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions.

At highly basic pH value of the solution, the heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions can exist in the form of hydroxide complex which reduces adsorption ability of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. Secondly at highly acidic pH value of the solution, all of the lone pair of adsorbent can be coordinated with protons so it reduces adsorption ability of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. Both these conditions are responsible for low adsorption of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. The adsorption ability of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite is increased at average pH value of the solution.

The adsorption ability of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite is large at average pH value because at average pH value lone pairs of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite are free to coordinate with heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions. Secondly, at average pH value, metal ions did not exist as hydroxide complex and these metal ions can be absorbed by MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. Due to these two reasons MIL-101-1,2-

Dichloroethane composite do not show maximum adsorption at extreme pH values, so the adsorption efficiency of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite is maximum at pH 6.

4. Conclusion

It is analysed with help of qualitative and quantitative analysis that, MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite has great capabilities for adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions. Langmuir and Freundlich model reveals the adsorption of metals. Freundlich model more effectively explain adsorption of heavy metals. Freundlich model reveals that multilayer adsorption of heavy metal (Lead and Cadmium) ions on surface of MIL-101-1,2-Dichloroethane composite. The adsorption was maximum at pH = 6. It was found that all the metal ions adsorption is done with accuracy when metal ions are in very low concentrations. This offers a simple, rapid, sensitive and cheap method that promotes the spirit of green chemistry in chemical quantitative analysis.

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